

**DIPLOMACY OF THE BUKHARA KHANATE AND THE BABURIAN
DYNASTY**

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Yursinboyev Jahongir son of Mehrojiddin

Student of Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute

Toshtemirova Saodat Abdurashidovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Annotation: This article provides some information on the foreign diplomatic and trade relations of the Bukhara Khanate and the Baburid dynasty. One of the main tasks is to analyze the historical stages that have been traversed so far in building a democratic society. A deeper understanding of the history of society and statehood and drawing the right conclusions from it can be one of the key factors in building an independent state.

Key words: Bukhara Khanate, Indian Ambassadors, A. Jenkinson, Erketi, Dzungars, trade, fruits, plants.

Introduction: Scientific research of the history of the Uzbek statehood, its objective assessment and creative use of the accumulated experience play an important role in the socio-political and cultural development of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, by the end of the twentieth century, a comprehensive study of the history of Uzbekistan, which is an integral part of world civilization, in particular, the history of Uzbek statehood, has risen to the level of public policy.

Therefore, in recent years, the issue of a clear and accurate historical approach to the study of a number of topical issues in the history of Uzbekistan has become increasingly important. It should be noted that the Bukhara Khanate, one of the Uzbek khanates, is a state that has left a great mark on the history of the Baburi, its social, economic, cultural life and international relations. The study requires separate scientific research.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Plays an important role in the study of Bukhara and the Baburid dynasty (including the relations of Central Asia with the neighboring countries of the East in the XXVIII century). They provide an analysis of economic and political relations, efforts to explore trade routes, and detailed information on which countries are importing which goods and in what quantities.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur also noted in his book "Boburnoma": "A banquet was held in honor of the ambassadors from neighboring Iran and the Shaybani state. They were presented with various gifts. Friendship and friendship between the three countries. an agreement on the establishment of permanent trade relations was signed."

The establishment of relations between the Baburid Empire in India and the Bukhara Khanate is associated with the names of Babur and the Immigrants. During the reign of Kochkunchikhan, the Bukhara Khanate recognized the Baburid state and established trade and embassy relations with it.

Results: Sources say that the emigrant ambassador brought to Babur 200 good horses, which were presented to Babur as a gift of seven camels loaded with famous raisins, subkhoni apricots and other rare blessings of Movarounnahr. Babur, in turn, sent ambassadors to the Bukhara khanate. Trade and embassy relations between the two countries continued during the reign of Babur's son Humayun. Such relations were further expanded during the subsequent Shaybani and Baburi rulers. For example, Bukhara Khan Abdullah II tried to work with the Baburis in the fight against the Safavids. Therefore, in 1572, Abdullah II sent ambassadors to Akbar Shah.

The ambassadors from Bukhara read gifts and letters from their ruler. After some time, they returned with gifts and letters. In his letter, Abdullah expressed a desire to strengthen friendly relations between the two countries. The aim was to form an alliance against the threat of an attack by other states.

Discussion: In addition, F. Beneveni, in his research, gives information about the connection of Bukhara with the Baburid dynasty. and the cessation of trade through Balkh, and the cessation of caravans to Kabul, Lahore, and India for the fourth year in a row.

F. Beneveni sends his servant Miner to Balkh and Badakhshan in the guise of a merchant to find and locate gold and silver deposits. According to him, more Bukhara goods were sold there, and traders received payment for these goods in the form of gold and silver bars from the people of Badakhshan.

Beneveni's servant Miner was amazed by the Russian goods in the markets of Balkh and Badakhshan: pineapple, mirrors, scissors, beads, watercress, beaver, furs and skins, green, red and dark blue mauve. He writes that caravans loaded with gold and silver from Badakhshan via Balkh went to Mashhad 2, 3 and even 4 times a year. In Khorasan, they were converted into gold and silver coins, which were used to buy Iranian goods for Central Asia.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be noted that the diplomatic relations of the Bukhara Khanate and the Baburid dynasty have been studied in detail and in depth. We will be sure once again. Also, our great ancestor Babur and the Buburi dynasty tried and succeeded not only in establishing relations with the Bukhara Khanate, but also with Europe, establishing diplomatic relations.

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